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Marketing is an activity of a person aimed at satisfying demand and need through means of exchange. Marketing includes business activities related to market research, planning the range of products according to the customer's order, market capture, advertising, delivery of goods and services from the manufacturer to the consumer. Marketing allows designers, engineers, economists and other professionals to get acquainted with the needs of the market, to think about what the consumer wants the product to be, how much to pay for it, and who needs it. The emergence of marketing elements dates back to the mid-seventeenth century. By this time, various forms of natural exchange of goods appeared, followed by the development of the first elements of marketing activities, such as advertising, pricing, sales.

Marketing is not only a field of philosophy, way of thinking and economic

MARKETING ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses what marketing is, what is the main reason for organization of marketing, the main purpose of marketing, the main tasks that marketing should perform, the main purpose of the firm, marketing organization and management, marketing strategy and its stages, as well as what is included in the marketing package carried.

thinking, but also a practical activity for individual firms, companies, industries and the economy as a whole. There are many types of marketing definitions in the economic literature of the United States and other countries. The most common definition of marketing, given by the American Marketing Association, is as follows: "Marketing is the process by which an idea is planned and implemented, prices are set, The movement and sale of goods and services, the goals of individual individuals and organizations are met through the exchange".

Marketing is a type of human activity aimed at satisfying needs and wants through exchange. Marketing can also be seen as a means between the emergence of a product and a service and the end of its life cycle. One of the main reasons for the emergence of marketing is the increase in production, the emergence of new industries, the expansion of the

range of goods and the problem of selling products among entrepreneurs. The emergence of marketing is also due to the growth of small enterprises, such as management, and thus the sharp competition between large enterprises. The main directions of comprehensive market research on the basis of marketing are as follows:

- demand study;
- determine the market structure;
- study of goods;
- study of competitive conditions;
- Analysis of forms and methods of sales.

Marketing is a method of working in the market of enterprises, market methodology, the study of consumers and their needs, the creation of appropriate goods, pricing, methods of delivery, supply, sale, organization of services, tools, procedures is a set of rules. All this serves the first main purpose, which is to coordinate supply and demand. Under market conditions, enterprise management puts marketing at the beginning of the production cycle, because economic decisions are based not on production opportunities, but on market requirements, customer needs. Therefore, the market determines the size of the enterprise, the organizational structure of the enterprise management, the principles and methods of management, the direction of services.

The purpose of marketing is to bring high benefits to organizations based on the organization of production by adapting production to the needs of the customer and achieving a balance of supply and demand. To achieve this, marketing must address the following important tasks:

- study and identify consumer needs;
- adjusting price performance to consumer needs;
- market research based primarily on supply and demand data;
- organization of product advertising, increasing consumer interest in purchasing goods;
- data collection and analysis for price research by the manufacturer or seller;
- obtain information on all services in the marketing of goods;
- Identify the strengths and weaknesses of one type of product produced by the enterprise over the same type of goods produced by another enterprise and eliminate its weaknesses;
- creating the necessary conditions for regular customers;
- collection of information on complements and substitutes;
- forecasting the demand for goods, controlling their sale.

Marketing or business activities are carried out in order to achieve a clear result. The main goals of marketing are interrelated with the main goals of the firm. The main objectives of the company are:

- market capture;
- profitability;
- financial stability;
- ensuring the social factors of production;
- Establish and strengthen the existing level in the market.

“Analysis of marketing goals allows you to formulate key objectives to achieve them. In 1986, Meffert identified three interrelated marketing challenges:

1. Tasks related to market activity related to demand regulation.

2. Tasks related to the field of the firm or enterprise.

3. Issues related to the external environment and community organizations.”[1]

Marketing organization is the organizational structure of the departments that manage the marketing service, which determines the subordination and responsibility for the performance of this or that task. “Marketing can be done in several ways:

1. Functional - in this case, the responsibility falls on the distribution, sales, supply and organization of the movement of goods.

2. Organization on the principle of goods. It adds a new team to the functional principles for another brand.

3. Market-based organization. It adds to its functional principles the governors of other regional markets and types of consumers.”[2]

The steps of a marketing strategy are:

1. Study of demand conjuncture. The company studies the economic situation in the market, ie the potential of consumers.

2. Study market capacity. The company determines the sales capacity in the market. This reduces risk and prevents overhead.

3. Defining the goals and capabilities of the enterprise in the current market conditions. Knowing the needs of the market allows you to compare them with the capabilities of the enterprise. That is, it helps the company set a achievable goal and develop a strategy accordingly.

4. Develop a marketing plan and strategy. It is developed as a general strategy to achieve the goal, as well as a

detailed plan for the direction and divisions of the enterprise.

5. Scientific, technical and experimental design work. Once the development path has been identified in 4 stages, research, experimental and design work, technology, production plan, supply and process will be transferred to the production of products for direct sale. Finally, the product is created.

6. Product launch. The most important condition for this is not only to choose the most optimal way to enter the market, but also to determine the pricing policy.

7. You can't succeed in the market without thinking and acting effectively. Informing consumers about the product and encouraging them to buy it is a complex and responsible task, and at the same time it is necessary to take care of sales promotion.

8. Product range management. Exploring consumer demand for new product ranges. Adapt to the whims of consumers and the market by changing, updating or replacing the range.

9. Trade Management. Special attention is paid to trade, transportation and packaging. In addition, the market seeks to gain a foothold for consumer sales and movement.

10. After-sales service, customer service, assistance in the use of goods.

11. Monitoring of marketing activities. Monitor and analyze the entire activity program. The final stage means the re-start of the first stage.

Marketing management is the study and analysis of production and market profit, to increase sales, to provide profitable exchanges with customers in order to increase market share, to

strengthen. In other words, marketing management is demand management.

The enterprise must create a marketing system that carries out all marketing activities and planning. If it is a small business, marketing should be done by one person. It conducts marketing research, organizes sales and advertising, and provides customer service. If the business is large, the marketing department will provide marketing services. The department employs agents, marketing researchers, advertising specialists, product managers, market segment managers, and customer service staff.

A marketing mix is a combination of four components: product, price, distribution, and sales promotion. In order to carry out all marketing activities, it is necessary to create four systems in

production - marketing information, marketing planning, organization of marketing services and marketing control. All of this makes up the marketing management process.

In today's market economy, competition is fierce in every field. The survival of enterprises and firms depends on how well they conduct their policies. Whereas previously produced goods and services were sold, today they are produced goods and services that are in high demand by consumers who are clearly on sale. Therefore, to study such market vagaries, competitors' strategies, economic, social, geographical, national and traditional values, needs and requirements of consumers, to enable the enterprise or firm to make optimal decisions by avoiding various unprofitable expenses marketing services should be used.

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